

Evaluation of marketing supply chain performance of fresh vegetables in Allahabad district, India

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Abstract

The present study was carried out in Allahabad district, Uttar Pradesh, India during November, 2011 to March, 2012 to evaluate the existing marketing supply chains of fresh tomato, cabbage and cauliflower (SC₁: Producer – Consumer; SC₂: Producer - Retailer – Consumer; SC₃: Producer - Commission agent - Retailer – Consumer and SC₄: Producer - Commission agent -Wholesaler - Retailer - Consumer). The marketing supply chains had significant effect on net marketing price of producer, net profit of producer, total marketing cost, total marketing loss, total net marketing margin, marketing efficiency, producer share in consumer price and consumer purchase price of fresh tomato, cabbage and cauliflower. The gross marketing price, net marketing price and net profit of producer for fresh tomato, cabbage and cauliflower were significantly higher in marketing supply chain SC₁, followed by SC₂, SC₃ and SC₄. The marketing cost, marketing loss, marketing margin and consumer purchase price for tomato, cabbage and cauliflower were significantly higher in marketing supply chain SC₄, followed by SC₃, SC₂ and SC₁. The standardized beta co-efficient revealed that commission charges for marketing of tomato, cabbage and cauliflower was the most important factor, which influenced the marketing cost, followed by transportation, rent, electricity and labour, packaging and loading and unloading expenses. Marketing efficiency and producer share in consumer price for tomato, cabbage and cauliflower were significantly higher in marketing supply chains SC₁, followed by SC₂, SC₃, and SC₄. The results revealed that the net profit of the producer, marketing efficiency and producer share in consumer price decreased significantly; whereas marketing cost, marketing loss and consumer purchase price increased significantly with the increase in number of intermediaries in marketing supply chains. In order to provide higher net profit to producer and competitive price to consumer for tomato, cabbage and cauliflower, it is important to introduce single window marketing system as well as provide better facilities for storage, transportation and marketing of tomato, cabbage and cauliflower.

Keywords: tomato, cabbage, cauliflower, supply chain, marketing cost, marketing loss, marketing efficiency, producer share in consumer price.

Introduction

Fresh vegetables play an important role for human health and economy of the nation. The Vegetables are highly perishable, which cannot be stored for long periods without proper post harvest facilities and efficient management system. India is the second largest producer of vegetables in the world. India's production of vegetables currently stands at 126 million tonnes, making up for around 14% of world production (National Horticultural Board, Govt. of India, 2010). The suitable agro-climatic condition has enormous potential for wide variety of vegetable production in Uttar Pradesh. The

present share of Uttar Pradesh in total horticultural production of the country is approximately 26%. Uttar Pradesh ranks 2nd in vegetables production among all states, The major vegetables grown in Uttar Pradesh are potato, peas, chilli, okra, tomato, brinjal (egg plant), cauliflower, cabbage, spinach, radish, carrot, turnip, onion and cucurbits, etc (State Horticulture Mission, Uttar Pradesh, 2011). The majority of farmers in Uttar Pradesh are either marginal or small-scale. The State Government of Uttar Pradesh has introduced various schemes and policies to facilitate the production and marketing of horticultural crops as well as to improve socio-economic condition of small scale farmers.

However, the economic condition of majority of the marginal and small-scale farmers has not improved due to poor unevolved marketing systems, large numbers of intermediaries in supply chain, poor logistics and storage facilities, lack of food processing industries, high fluctuation in price, etc. In the present scenario, the small and marginal farmers are most exploited due to lack of proper marketing supply chain system and poor linkage between farmer and potential market (Meer 2005; Berdegue et al., 2008; Cavatassi et al., 2009).

Supply chain management is a wide business process encompassing planning, implementing and controlling the operations of the supply chain which aims at providing the consumers with desirable goods and commodities. Supply chain management includes movement and storage of raw materials, inventory and finished goods from producers to consumers. Supply chain management can be explained as the flow of plans, materials and services from the supplier to the consumer including the close cooperation between the various entities in supply chain. An efficient supply chain management contributes to improve efficiency in production, value additions, storage, transportation and marketing, which in turn maximize the profitability of the chain partners and minimize the purchasing cost of consumers. The major issues in existing marketing supply chain of fresh vegetables in India are high marketing cost, high marketing loss, low marketing efficiency and producer's share in consumer price as well as high consumer price (Chauhan et al. 1998; Ladaniya et al. 2005; Pawar and Pawar 2005; Talathi et al. 2005; Zulfiqar et al. 2005; Murthy et al. 2007; Gangwar et al. 2007; Sidhu et al. 2010; Emam 2011; Pandey et al. 2011; Hena and Soni, 2013).

The trading of fresh vegetables is complicated due to its high perishability and therefore it is a great challenge for the producers, suppliers, processors, exporters and traders to maintain the desirable quality for domestic consumption as well as export. Due to highly perishable in nature, the major constraint in vegetable business is the large postharvest losses during transportation and marketing. The marketing cost, marketing loss and marketing efficiency of fresh vegetables in India is

largely affected by the poor infrastructure and lack of linkages between producer and intermediaries in the supply chain. The marketing efficiency of fresh vegetables is also affected by the substantial amount of wastage, deterioration in quality, mismatch in supply and demand and fluctuation in price. High perishability, seasonal in nature and bulkiness make the marketing of fresh vegetables extremely complex (Anil and Arora 1999; Gupta and Rathore 1999; More 1999; Begum and Raha 2002; Sudha et al. 2002; Murthy et al. 2002; Singh and Chauhan 2004; Bala 2006; Lu 2006; Murthy et al. 2007; Rupali and Gyan 2010; Barakade et al. 2011).

India is the first largest producer of cauliflower and second largest producer of tomato and cabbage in the world. Tomato, cabbage and cauliflower are economically important and popular vegetables in India. The marketing supply chains for tomato, cabbage and cauliflower in the state of Uttar Pradesh particularly in Allahabad district is traditional which involved significant number of intermediaries, resulting to high marketing cost, high marketing loss, low marketing efficiency, low producers share in consumer price and high consumer purchase price. In spite of economic importance of production of tomato, cabbage and cauliflower in Allahabad district, Uttar Pradesh, little information is available on marketing supply chain management. Therefore the objectives of the study were to evaluate existing marketing supply chains of tomato, cabbage and cauliflower in relation to producer net marketing price, net profit of producer, marketing cost, marketing loss, marketing margin, marketing efficiency, producer share in consumer price and consumer purchase price in order to identify major constraints and opportunities to develop efficient marketing system.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted in Allahabad district (25.45°N, 81.84°E, 98 m above mean sea level), Uttar Pradesh, India during November, 2011 to March, 2012 to examine the existing marketing supply chains of fresh tomato, cabbage and cauliflower. The marketing supply chain of tomato, cabbage and cauliflower consist of various intermediaries such as commission agents,

wholesalers and retailers who move the fresh produce from producer / farmer to consumer. The following marketing supply chains were analysed in the present study because these are commonly used marketing supply chains for tomato, cabbage and cauliflower in Allahabad district, India.

- SC₁: Producer → Consumer
 SC₂: Producer → Retailer → Consumer
 SC₃: Producer → Commission Agent →
 Retailer → Consumer
 SC₄: Producer → Commission Agent → → →
 Wholesaler → Retailer → Consumer

The primary data for evaluation of above mentioned marketing supply chains of tomato, cabbage and cauliflower in relation to transportation, packaging and marketing costs, spoilage during transportation and marketing, loading, unloading and commission charges, cleaning, washing and grading charges, sale price, problems faced and expectations of producers, commission agents, wholesalers, retailers and consumers were collected by using well structured questionnaires. During the survey ten producers, ten commission agents, ten wholesalers, ten retailers and twenty consumers for each marketing supply chain were interviewed and data were collected.

The producer net marketing price (NMP_p), net profit of producer (NP_p), net marketing margin of wholesaler (NMM_w), net marketing margin of retailer (NMM_r), total net marketing margin (TNMM), total marketing cost (TMC), total marketing loss (TML), marketing efficiency (ME as estimated by Shepherd 1965; Murthy et al. 2007; Acharya and Agarwal 2011) and producer share in consumer price (PSCP) four marketing supply chains of tomato, cabbage and cauliflower were estimated by the following methods :

$$NMP_p = GMP_p - [MC_p + PL_p \times GMP_p] \quad \dots (1)$$

$$NP_p = GMP_p - (CP + MC_p + PL_p \times GMP_p) \quad \dots(2)$$

$$NMM_w = SP_w - PR_w - (MC_w + PL_w \times PR_w) \quad \dots(3)$$

$$NMM_r = SP_r - PP_r - (MC_r + PL_r \times PP_r) \quad \dots(4)$$

$$TNMM = NMM_w + NMM_r \quad \dots(5)$$

$$TMC = MC_p + MC_w + MC_r \quad \dots(6)$$

$$TML = (PL_p \times GMP_p) + (PL_w \times PP_w) + (PL_r \times PP_r) \quad \dots(7)$$

Shepherd, 1965 :

$$ME = \frac{C_p}{TMC} - 1 \quad \dots(8)$$

Murthy et al., 2007:

$$ME = \frac{NMP_p}{TNMM + TMC + TML} \quad \dots(9)$$

Acharya and Agarwal, 2011 :

$$ME = \frac{NMP_p}{TNMM + TMC} \quad \dots(10)$$

$$PSCP = \frac{NMP_p}{C_p} \times 100 \quad \dots(11)$$

Where,

NMP_p = net marketing price received by producer (Rs/kg); GMP_p = gross marketing price received by producer (Rs/kg); MC_p = marketing cost of producer for transportation, packaging, loading and unloading and commission (Rs/kg); PL_p = physical loss of tomato, cabbage and cauliflower by producer during transportation and marketing (kg/kg); NP_p = net profit of producer (Rs/kg), CP = cost of production (Rs/kg); NMM_w = net marketing margin of wholesaler (Rs/Kg); SP_w = wholesaler sale price (Rs/kg); PP_w = purchase price of the wholesaler (Rs/kg); MC_w = marketing cost of wholesaler for transportation, packaging, loading and unloading, commission, rent, electricity and labour, etc (Rs/kg); PL_w = physical loss of tomato, cabbage and cauliflower by wholesaler during transportation and marketing(kg / kg); NMM_r = net marketing margin of retailer (Rs/Kg); SP_r = retailer sale price (Rs/kg); PP_r = purchase price of retailer (Rs/kg); MC_r = marketing cost of retailer for transportation, packaging, loading and unloading and commission, rent, electricity and labour etc. (Rs/kg); PL_r = physical loss of tomato, cabbage and cauliflower by retailer during transportation and marketing (Kg / kg); $TNMM$ = total net marketing margin (Rs/kg); TMC = total marketing Cost (Rs/kg); TML = total

marketing loss of tomato, cabbage and cauliflower (Rs/kg) ; ME = marketing efficiency; C_p = consumer price (Rs/kg) and $PSCP$ = producer share in consumer price (%).

The descriptive statistics, analysis of variance, post hoc tests for multiple comparisons of means and multiple regression were used to analyse the data. The analysis was performed with SPSS version 20.

Results and Discussion

The marketing supply chains had significant effect on gross marketing price, net marketing price and net profit of producer and consumer purchase price of tomato. The gross marketing price of producer (Rs. 15.50 Rs. / kg), net marketing price of producer (Rs. 14.14 Rs. / kg) and net profit of producer (Rs. 11.87 Rs. / kg) of fresh tomato was significantly higher in marketing supply chain SC_1 (Producer – Consumer), followed by SC_2 (Producer - Retailer – Consumer), SC_3 (Producer - Commission agent - Retailer – Consumer) and SC_4 (Producer - Commission agent -Wholesaler - Retailer - Consumer). The net marketing price of producer and net profit of producer decreased considerably in marketing supply chains SC_2 , SC_3 and SC_4 due to involvement of intermediaries in trading of fresh tomato. The consumer purchase price of fresh tomato was significantly lower in marketing supply chain SC_1 (Rs. 15.50 Rs. / kg) as compared with SC_2 (Rs. 19.40 Rs. / kg), SC_3 (Rs. 19.70 Rs. / kg) and SC_4 (Rs. 19.50 Rs. / kg). In case of marketing supply chain SC_1 , consumer directly purchase the fresh tomato from producer / farmer, whereas in case of marketing chains SC_2 , SC_3 and SC_4 , intermediaries such as commission agent, retailer and wholesaler were involved in trading of fresh tomato (Table 1). The similar trends as in case of fresh tomato for gross marketing price of producer, net marketing of producer, net profit of producer and consumer purchase price were also found for cabbage and cauliflower (Table 2 and 3).

Table 1. Gross marketing price, net marketing price and net profit of producer and consumer price of tomato in different marketing supply chains

Marketing supply chains	Gross marketing price of producer (GMP _P) Rs/kg	Net marketing price of producer (NMP _P) Rs/kg	Net profit of producer (NP _P) Rs/kg	Consumer price (C _P) Rs/kg
SC ₁	15.50 ^a	14.14 ^a	11.87 ^a	15.50 ^a
SC ₂	13.40 ^b	12.13 ^b	9.86 ^b	19.40 ^b
SC ₃	12.70 ^c	10.50 ^c	8.23 ^c	19.70 ^b
SC ₄	8.94 ^d	6.99 ^d	4.72 ^d	19.50 ^b

Values followed by same letter in superscript have no significant difference ($p < 0.05$)

Table 2. Gross marketing price, net marketing price and net profit of producer and consumer price of Cabbage in different marketing supply chains

Marketing supply chains	Gross marketing price of producer (GMP _P) Rs/kg	Net marketing price of producer (NMP _P) Rs/kg	Net profit of producer (NP _P) Rs/kg	Consumer price (C _P) Rs/kg
SC ₁	8.20 ^a	7.44 ^a	5.56 ^a	8.20 ^a
SC ₂	7.05 ^b	6.28 ^b	4.39 ^b	11.00 ^b
SC ₃	5.95 ^c	4.58 ^c	2.69 ^c	10.80 ^b
SC ₄	4.12 ^d	2.94 ^d	1.06 ^d	10.90 ^b

Values followed by same letter in superscript have no significant difference ($p < 0.05$)

Table 3. Gross marketing price, net marketing price and net profit of producer and consumer price of Cauliflower in different marketing supply chains

Marketing supply chains	Gross marketing price of producer (GMP _P) Rs/kg	Net marketing price of producer (NMP _P) Rs/kg	Net profit of producer (NP _P) Rs/kg	Consumer price (C _P) Rs/kg
SC ₁	10.50 ^a	9.52 ^a	5.75 ^a	10.50 ^a
SC ₂	9.58 ^b	8.74 ^b	4.97 ^b	13.80 ^b
SC ₃	8.10 ^c	6.71 ^c	2.94 ^c	13.70 ^b
SC ₄	6.27 ^d	5.03 ^d	1.26 ^d	13.75 ^b

Values followed by same letter in superscript have no significant difference ($p < 0.05$)

The overall results revealed that marketing supply chain SC₁ was the most efficient in terms of gross marketing price of producer, net marketing price of producer, net profit of producer and price paid by consumer for fresh tomato, cabbage and cauliflower, followed by marketing supply chains SC₂, SC₃ and SC₄. The results indicate that in order to improve the net profit of the producer and provide competitive price to consumer for fresh tomato, cabbage and cauliflower, it is necessary to reduce number of intermediaries in marketing supply chain by introducing cooperative marketing supply chain / strengthening marketing facilities for

direct sale to consumer by producer / farmer. Similar results were reported by many researchers for wide variety of vegetables / fruits and marketing supply chains (Chauhan et al. 1998; Pawar and Pawar 2005; Murthy et al. 2007; Sidhu et al. 2010; Pandey et al. 2011; Hena and Soni, 2013).

The marketing supply chains SC₁ (Producer - Consumer), SC₂ (Producer - Retailer - Consumer), SC₃ (Producer - Commission Agent - Retailer - Consumer) and SC₄ (Producer - Commission Agent - Wholesaler - Retailer - Consumer) significantly ($p < 0.05$) influenced the marketing cost, marketing

loss and marketing margin of fresh tomato. The total marketing cost of fresh tomato was significantly minimum in marketing supply chain SC₁ (0.54 Rs. / kg) and it increased significantly in marketing supply chains SC₂ (1.63 Rs. / kg), SC₃ (3.58 Rs. / kg) and SC₄ (3.97 Rs. / kg). The number of intermediaries (commission agent, wholesaler and retailer) in marketing supply chains SC₁, SC₂, SC₃ and SC₄ were 0, 1, 2 and 3 respectively. The results revealed that the total marketing cost of tomato increased considerably with the increase in number of intermediaries in marketing supply chains. This is due to fact that the expenses for packaging, transportation, loading, unloading, commission, rent, electricity and labour increases considerably with increase in number of intermediaries in marketing supply chain, which consequently increases the total marketing cost (Table 4). The total marketing loss which includes the physical loss of fresh tomato during transportation, loading, unloading and marketing by producer / farmer, wholesaler and retailer was significantly minimum in marketing supply chain SC₁ (0.82 Rs. / kg) and it increased significantly in marketing supply chains SC₂ (1.98 Rs. / kg), SC₃

(2.30 Rs. / kg) and SC₄ (2.85 Rs./kg). The results revealed that total marketing loss of fresh tomato increased significantly with the increase in number of intermediaries in marketing supply chain, because producer, wholesaler and retailer perform the logistic and marketing activities separately. The total net marketing margin, which includes net marketing margin of wholesaler and retailer for fresh tomato was significantly higher in marketing supply chain SC₄ (5.69 Rs. /kg), because in this supply chain, commission agent, wholesaler and retailer were involved in trading of fresh tomato, followed by SC₃ and SC₂ (Table 4). The effect of marketing supply chains on total marketing cost, total marketing loss and total net marketing margin of cabbage and cauliflower are presented in Table 5 and Table 6. In spite of some variation, similar trend as mentioned above for tomato was also observed for cabbage and cauliflower (Table 5 and 6).

Packaging, transportation, loading and unloading, commission and rent, electricity and labour expenses significantly influenced the marketing cost of fresh tomato. The multiple regression analysis for standardized

Table 4. Marketing cost, marketing loss and marketing margin of tomato as influenced by marketing supply chains

Marketing supply chains	Total marketing cost (TMC) Rs/kg	Total marketing loss (TML) Rs/kg	Total net marketing margin (TNMM) Rs/kg
SC ₁	0.54 ^a	0.82 ^a	0.00 ^a
SC ₂	1.63 ^b	1.98 ^b	3.66 ^b
SC ₃	3.58 ^c	2.30 ^c	3.23 ^c
SC ₄	3.97 ^d	2.85 ^d	5.69 ^d

Values followed by same letter in superscript have no significant difference ($p < 0.05$)

Table 5. Marketing cost, marketing loss and marketing margin of cabbage as influenced by marketing supply chains

Marketing supply chains	Total marketing cost (TMC) Rs/kg	Total marketing loss (TML) Rs/kg	Total net marketing margin (TNMM) Rs/kg
SC ₁	0.52 ^a	0.24 ^a	0.00 ^a
SC ₂	1.58 ^b	0.62 ^b	2.53 ^b
SC ₃	2.85 ^c	0.70 ^c	2.68 ^b
SC ₄	3.27 ^d	0.85 ^d	3.85 ^c

Values followed by same letter in superscript have no significant difference ($p < 0.05$)

Table 6. Marketing cost, marketing loss and marketing margin of cauliflower as influenced by marketing supply chains

Marketing supply chains	Total marketing cost (TMC) Rs/kg	Total marketing loss (TML) Rs/kg	Total net marketing margin (TNMM) Rs/kg
SC ₁	0.92 ^a	0.30 ^a	0.00 ^a
SC ₂	1.58 ^b	0.71 ^b	2.77 ^b
SC ₃	2.86 ^c	0.77 ^c	3.37 ^c
SC ₄	3.14 ^d	1.03 ^d	4.55 ^d

Values followed by same letter in superscript have no significant difference ($p < 0.05$)

beta coefficient revealed that the commission charges (0.551) paid to commission agent by producer and wholesaler / retailer was the most important factor which influenced the marketing cost of fresh tomato, followed by transportation (0.219), rent, electricity and labour (0.179), packaging (0.103) and loading and unloading (0.076) expenses (Table 7). In spite of some variation, the results on effect of packaging, transportation, loading and unloading, commission and rent, electricity

and labour expenses on marketing cost of fresh cabbage and cauliflower showed similar trends as in case of fresh tomato (Table 8 and 9). The results clearly indicate that in order to reduce the marketing cost of fresh tomato, cabbage and cauliflower, it is necessary to minimize expenses for transportation, commission, packaging, loading, unloading, rent, electricity and labour by providing appropriate and effective logistic system to producer / farmer and intermediaries (Table 7, 8 and 9).

Table 7. Multiple regression results to explain the effect of logistics on marketing cost of tomato in different marketing supply chains

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.001	.007		.198	.844
	Packaging	1.018	.055	.103	18.441	.000
	Transportation	.998	.022	.219	44.507	.000
	Loading and Unloading	.981	.069	.076	14.131	.000
	Commission Charges	.993	.005	.551	197.560	.000
	Rent, Electricity & Labour	1.019	.018	.179	55.501	.000

a Dependent Variable: Marketing Cost

Table 8. Multiple regression results to explain the effect of logistics on marketing cost of cabbage in different marketing supply chains

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.011	.013		-.841	.406
	Packaging	.956	.102	.100	9.333	.000
	Transportation	1.068	.040	.287	26.680	.000
	Loading and Unloading	.920	.078	.127	11.763	.000
	Commission Charges	1.003	.014	.360	70.178	.000
	Rent, Electricity and Labour	.985	.033	.229	29.443	.000

a Dependent Variable: Marketing cost

Table 9. Multiple regression results to explain the effect of logistics on marketing cost of cauliflower in different marketing supply chains

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.003	.013		-.222	.826
	Packaging	1.022	.080	.082	12.788	.000
	Transportation	1.006	.048	.208	21.074	.000
	Loading and Unloading	.982	.072	.101	13.612	.000
	Commission charges	.988	.009	.546	104.651	.000
	Rent, Electricity and Labour	1.012	.025	.224	40.743	.000

a Dependent Variable: Marketing cost

The overall results revealed that marketing cost, marketing loss and marketing margin increased significantly ($p < 0.05$) with the increase in number of intermediaries in marketing supply chain, which in turn significantly reduced the net profit of producer as well as increased the consumer purchase price of fresh tomato, cabbage and cauliflower. The results further revealed that transportation cost, commission charges and rent, electricity and labour expenses were the important

factors, which influenced the marketing cost of fresh tomato, cabbage and cauliflower. The lack of appropriate and efficient transportation, storage, grading, packaging and marketing facilities and mismatch between supply and demand as well as poor coordination between producer and intermediaries resulted in considerable physical loss of fresh tomato, cabbage and cauliflower. The similar results were also reported by many researches for fresh vegetables and fruits under

wide range of marketing supply chains (Sudha et al. 2002; Zulfiqar et al. 2005; Murthy et al. 2007; Gangwar et al. 2007; Sidhu et al. 2010; Pandey et al. 2011; Hena and Soni 2013).

The marketing supply chains SC₁ (Producer - Consumer), SC₂ (Producer - Retailer - Consumer), SC₃ (Producer - Commission Agent - Retailer - Consumer) and SC₄ (Producer - Commission Agent - Wholesaler - Retailer - Consumer) had significant effect on marketing efficiency and producer share in consumer price for fresh tomato. The marketing efficiency estimated by three different methods (Shepherd 1965; Murthy et al. 2007; Acharya and Agarwal 2011) were significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) in marketing supply chain SC₁, followed by SC₂, SC₃ and SC₄ for fresh tomato. The results clearly indicate that marketing efficiency estimated by Shepherd (1965), Murthy et al. (2007) and Acharya and Agarwal (2011) approaches decreased significantly with the increase in number of intermediaries in marketing supply chains of fresh tomato. This is due to fact that marketing cost, marketing loss, marketing margin and consumer purchase price increased significantly as well as net marketing price of producer and net profit of producer decreased significantly with increase in number of intermediaries in marketing supply chains of fresh tomato (Table 10). The producer share in consumer price for fresh tomato was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) in marketing supply chain SC₁ (91.25%) due to significantly higher net marketing price of producer and lower consumer purchase price, followed by marketing supply chains SC₂ (62.52%), SC₃ (53.25%) and SC₄ (35.85%). The results revealed that producer share

in consumer price decreased significantly (91.25% to 35.85%) with increase in number of intermediaries (0 to 3) in marketing supply chains mainly due to significant decrease in net marketing price of producer (Table 10). The similar trends for the effect of marketing supply chains on marketing efficiency and producer share in consumer price as observed for tomato were also found for cabbage and cauliflower (Table 11 and 12).

The overall results revealed that marketing efficiency and producer share in consumer price decreased considerably as the number of intermediaries increases in marketing supply chains due considerable increase in marketing cost, marketing loss, marketing margin and consumer purchase price as well as significant decrease in net marketing price of producer and net profit of producer. The results clearly indicate that marketing supply chain SC₁ was most efficient in terms of marketing efficiency and producer share in consumer price because no intermediaries were involved in trading of fresh tomato, cabbage and cauliflower. Therefore, in order to improve the marketing efficiency and producer share in consumer price, it is necessary to reduce the number of intermediaries in marketing supply chains as well as to reduce marketing cost and marketing loss by providing appropriate and efficient logistic and marketing facilities to supply chain partners. Similar results were also reported by many researches for wide varieties of fresh vegetables / fruits and marketing supply chains (Ladaniya et al. 2005; Murthy et al. 2007; Gangwar et al. 2007; Emam 2011; Pandey et al. 2011; Gaurav, 2011, Hena and Soni 2013).

Table 10. Marketing efficiency and producer share in consumer price for tomato in different marketing supply chains

Marketing supply chains	Marketing efficiency			Producer share in consumer price, %
	Shepherd (1965)	Murthy et al. (2007)	Acharya and Agarwal (2011)	
SC ₁	27.88 ^a	10.46 ^a	26.36 ^a	91.25 ^a
SC ₂	10.95 ^b	1.67 ^b	2.30 ^b	62.52 ^b
SC ₃	4.15 ^c	1.14 ^c	1.52 ^{bc}	53.25 ^c
SC ₄	3.91 ^c	0.56 ^d	0.73 ^c	35.85 ^d

Values followed by same letter in superscript have no significant difference ($p < 0.05$).

Table 11. Marketing efficiency and producer share in consumer price for cabbage in different marketing supply chains

Marketing supply chains	Marketing efficiency			Producer share in consumer price, %
	Shepherd (1965)	Murthy et al. (2007)	Acharya and Agarwal (2011)	
SC ₁	14.77 ^a	9.76 ^a	14.31 ^a	90.69 ^a
SC ₂	5.99 ^b	1.33 ^b	1.53 ^b	57.05 ^b
SC ₃	2.79 ^c	0.74 ^c	0.83 ^c	42.39 ^c
SC ₄	2.33 ^d	0.37 ^d	0.41 ^d	26.96 ^d

Values followed by same letter in superscript have no significant difference ($p < 0.05$)

Table 12. Marketing efficiency and producer share in consumer price for cauliflower in different marketing supply chains

Marketing supply chains	Marketing efficiency			Producer share in consumer price, %
	Shepherd (1965)	Murthy et al. (2007)	Acharya and Agarwal (2011)	
SC ₁	14.33 ^a	9.67 ^a	13.89 ^a	90.62 ^a
SC ₂	7.75 ^b	1.74 ^b	2.02 ^b	63.33 ^b
SC ₃	3.80 ^c	0.96 ^c	1.08 ^c	49.00 ^c
SC ₄	3.38 ^c	0.58 ^d	0.66 ^c	36.59 ^d

Values followed by same letter in superscript have no significant difference ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusions

The most important issues of existing marketing supply chains of fresh tomato, cabbage and cauliflower in Allahabad district are high marketing cost, marketing loss and marketing margin of intermediaries as well as low net profit of producer, marketing efficiency and producer share in consumer price. The study analysed four marketing supply chains of fresh tomato, cabbage and cauliflower to identify major constraints and opportunities in order to develop efficient marketing systems. The marketing supply chains had significant effect on marketing cost, marketing loss, marketing margin, net profit of producer, marketing efficiency and producer share in consumer price for fresh tomato, cabbage and cauliflower. The net marketing price of producer, net profit of producer, marketing efficiency and producer share in consumer price for fresh tomato, cabbage and

cauliflower were significantly higher in marketing supply chain SC₁, followed by SC₂, SC₃ and SC₄. The marketing cost and marketing loss of fresh tomato, cabbage and cauliflower were significantly higher in marketing supply chain SC₄, followed by SC₃, SC₂ and SC₁. The results clearly indicate that net profit of producer, marketing efficiency and producer share in consumer price decreased significantly as well as marketing cost and marketing loss increased significantly with the increase in number of intermediaries in marketing supply chains of fresh tomato, cabbage and cauliflower. Apart from net price of producer, marketing loss and marketing margin of intermediaries, the marketing cost was the most important factor influencing marketing efficiency and producer share in consumer price. The commission paid by producer and retailer / wholesaler to commission agent was the most

dominant factor influencing marketing cost of fresh tomato, cabbage and cauliflower.

In order to develop efficient and sustainable marketing system for fresh tomato, cabbage and cauliflower in Allahabad district, India, it is important to provide accurate market information regarding supply and demand, proper storage, grading and packaging facilities, efficient transportation and logistics system, credit and insurance facilities, etc. to producer and intermediaries involved in marketing supply chains. Furthermore, producers, wholesalers and retailers should be provided necessary logistics and financial support to transport fresh tomato, cabbage and cauliflower to neighbouring cities / states in order to control fluctuation in price and demand. The study clearly revealed that the number of intermediaries in the marketing supply chains is the major cause for low marketing efficiency and producer share in consumer price and high consumer purchase price. Therefore, it is important to evolve a single window marketing system such as cooperative marketing system for fresh tomato, cabbage and cauliflower in Allahabad district in order to improve the socio economic condition of small and marginal farmers / producers and provide competitive price to the consumers.

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